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EFFECT OF COLOR VARIATION ON CONSUMER SATISFACTION WITH CHOICE: THE CASE OF FASHION- AND STYLE-ORIENTED PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Iyengar and Lepper (2000) demonstrated that consumers are more likely to purchase gourmet jams or chocolates when offered a limited array of six choices, rather than a more extensive array of 24 or 30 choices; this finding appears, somewhat, to contradict the assumption that providing consumers with more choices is better. Moreover, those participants actually reported greater subsequent satisfaction with their selections when their original set of options had been limited. The present study analyzed the effect of color-variation offering in fashion- and style-oriented products (e.g., bags, sandals, and fountain pens) on consumer satisfaction. Our preliminary results showed that in terms of catering to participant preference, the optimal color-variation offering of a fashion- and style-oriented product was approximately 12-18 colors.

Keywords: fashion products, style products

INTRODUCTION

The offering to consumers of a variety of product colors has recently become an emphasis in marketing (Cooper and Matthews 2000; Kahn and Wasink 2004; Tokinaga and Utaunomiya 2009), and some products—such as digital cameras—are now offered in more than 100 colors. On the other hand, some studies show that consumers are most satisfied with their selections when relatively limited set of options are offered (Iyengar and Lepper 2000; Rozin 2005; Rozin et al .2006;). For example, a study by Iyengar and Lepper (2000) found that consumers were less satisfied when 30 flavors of jams were displayed in the store than only 6 flavors. Regarding products,

Tsuchiya et al. (2010) studied the effect of color-variation offering on style- and/or function-oriented products (e.g., watches, cell phones, and digital cameras) on consumer satisfaction; they suggest that an offering of approximately 6-12 colors may be optimal in terms of consumer choice. The present study examined the effect of color-variation offering among fashion- and style-oriented products (bags, sandals, and fountain pens) on consumer satisfaction.

METHODS

Ninety undergraduate students majoring in design participated in the study (62 females and 28 males; average age = 21.3 years).

Three kinds of products were used as visual stimuli: bags, sandals, and fountain pens. The products were classified as follows:

- Style-oriented products: fountain pens
- Fashion-oriented products: sandals
- Style- and fashion-oriented products: bags

Because both males and females participated in the study, only products featuring a unisex design were used. The brand name/product name of these three product categories are listed below; in the real commercial market, each of these products is offered in many different colors.

- Fountain pens: LAMY/safari
- Bags: Marc Jacobs/tote bag
- Sandals: Crocs/beach

The stimuli were presented in line drawings on paper (Figures 1-3). Six colors were printed on A4-size paper. Meanwhile, 12 colors were printed on A3-size paper, and 48 colors were printed on four sheets of A3-size paper.

Figure 1. Stimulation example of fountain pens

Figure 2. Stimulation example of sandals

Figure 3. Stimulation example of bags

In the experiment, each participant viewed the products in 6, 12, or 48 colors, and chose her/his favorite color for each product. To counterbalance the presentation order of the products, the participants were divided into three groups: Group A started with 6 colors of bags, Group B started with 12 colors of fountain pens, and Group C started with 48 colors of sandals.

After choosing a color for each product, each participant was asked to fill out a questionnaire. The questions were as follows:

- Pleasure: How much enjoyment did you feel when you chose it?
- Anxiety: How much anxiety did you feel when you chose it?
- Satisfaction: How much satisfaction did you feel with your choice?
- Value: How much did you want to buy the product?

The participants answered the questions via a seven-point Likert scale. They were then asked from how many colors they would most like to choose. After completing the questionnaire, each participant chose the next product. This procedure was repeated until each participant had completed the questionnaire for the third product.

RESULTS

For fountain pens and sandals, the pleasure of choice decreased as the size of the color-variation offering increased. However, for bags, the pleasure of choice increased as the color-variation offering increased in size (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Results: pleasure of choice

For all products, difficulty and anxiety of choice increased significantly as the size of the color-variation offering increased (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Results: anxiety of choice

For sandals, satisfaction with choice increased significantly as the size of the color-variation offering increased (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Results: satisfaction with choice

For fountain pens, value also increased significantly as the size of the color-variation offering increased (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Results: value

Regarding the optimal number of product colors offered, the most frequently cited numbers among the participants for fountain pens, bags, and sandals were approximately 18, 12, and 12, respectively (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Results: optimal number of colors offered

DISCUSSION

In line with the findings of Iyengar and Lepper (2000), the results of the current experiment showed that both the pleasure of choice and anxiety increased as the size of the color-variation offering increased. However, Iyengar and Lepper's (2000) study was with

regard to food products, and consumers may prefer having a little more variety of choice for products than for food. Let us examine the results vis-à-vis each of the stimulation products, in greater detail.

- Fountain pens

For fountain pens, the participants' value increased significantly as color variation increased; however, anxiety of choice increased concurrently. It was found from the results that the participants' optimal size of color-variation offering for fountain pens was approximately 18 colors.

- Sandals

For sandals, the participants' satisfaction of choice increased significantly as the size of color-variation offering increased; however, anxiety of choice, again, increased concurrently. In contrast, both pleasure of choice and value increased as the color variation decreased. It was found from the results that the participants' preferred size of color-variation offering for sandals was approximately 12 colors.

- Bags

For bags, both pleasure of choice and value increased as the size of the color-variation offering increased; again, however, anxiety of choice increased concurrently. Bags are both fashion- and style-oriented products, and so it makes sense that results with respect to them are in the "middle ground" between those for fountain pens and sandals.

CONCLUSION

The present study examined the effect of the size of color-variation offering on consumer satisfaction, with regard to fashion- and style-oriented products (e.g., bags, sandals, and fountain pens). The results showed that the participants' preferred sizes of color-variation offering with regard to such products were in the range of 12-18 colors. In addition, factors relating to certain trade-offs were observed. As a marketer or producer of goods, it may not necessarily be a good thing to increase the size of the color-variation offering of the products being sold. Future research will address these results from the viewpoints of consumer personality and lifestyle.

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